

Moldovan Framework of Cross-Border Cooperation: Legal and Historical Approaches

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Abstract. *The paper focuses on Moldovan experience of cross-border cooperation from legal and historical perspectives. Cross-border cooperation initiatives refer to the European Union, Romania and Ukraine. The research investigation examines legal instruments of cross-border cooperation between Moldova and its neighbours, cross-border cooperation programmes and the impact of cross-border cooperation projects towards sustainable development in adjacent areas by helping to reduce differences in standards and by addressing common specific challenges across Moldovan state border. The results and impact of cross-border cooperation are scrutinized through the prism of goals' achievement and de facto engagement leading to learned lessons by actors and revised design for improvement strategy.*

Keywords: *cross-border cooperation, Moldova, Romania, Ukraine, European Union, Euroregion, cooperation programme.*

Introduction

By underlying that cross-border cooperation brings positive changes in the lives of borderlanders, Moldovan policies in this area are congruent with the trends in the region. For almost three decades Moldova has been participating in cross-border cooperation initiatives implemented in cooperation with neighbour partners.

Considering geographical position of Moldova, historical links established by peoples and trade exchanges, it is worth mentioning that cross-border cooperation has been developed by immediate neighbours: the European Union, Romania, to the West and Ukraine to the East. The state of affairs is explained by the landlocked country status between Romania and Ukraine. Nevertheless, cross-border cooperation is not limited to these two countries, but even includes transnational collaboration in the South Eastern Europe initiatives in this specific area.

Moldova is an integral part of cross-border cooperation processes driven and backed by the European Union. Throughout the years it seems that cross-border cooperation is a key element of the EU policy towards its neighbours facing common challenges across land and water borders¹. Moreover, cross-border cooperation provided by the European Union is not confined only to common borderland challenges, but also helps neighbours in building institutional capacities and improving socio-economic standards. Cross-border cooperation is designed on the principles of territorial cooperation pattern; however, it is adapted to the specificities of external cooperation addressed to the

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¹ The recognition of shared land and water crossing challenges came by two major acts: Regulation (EC) No. 1638/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 2006 laying down general provisions establishing a European Neighbourhood and Partnership Instrument, OJ L310, 09.11.2006; Regulation (EU) No 232/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 2014 establishing a European Neighbourhood Instrument, OJ L77, 15.03.2014.

EU neighbours. Cross-border cooperation has specific characteristics of a unique cooperation mechanism demonstrated by strong commitment and ownership of the participating countries in such initiatives: balanced partnership between the Member States and neighbouring countries, jointly management entrusted authority, common framework and rules. Cross-border cooperation follows three basic objectives: to promote economic and social development in border areas, to address common challenges (environment, public health, safety and security), and to put in place better conditions for persons, goods and capital mobility². In the Eastern Partnership countries, the commitments of involved partners in achieving tangible results include four main priority areas: stronger economy (economic development and market opportunities); stronger governance (strengthening institutions and good governance); stronger connectivity (connectivity, energy efficiency, environment and climate change); stronger society (mobility and people-to-people contacts)³.

Identification of main priorities in cross-border cooperation resulted from common interests shared by neighbours. For research there are considered issues of cross-border cooperation, legal framework in cross-border cooperation, institutionalisation of cross-border cooperation, forms of cross-border cooperation, cross-border cooperation tools, cross-border cooperation projects' retrospective and impact evaluation of cross-border cooperation actions.

Cross-Border Cooperation

Cross-border cooperation in Europe is as old as the continent itself. However, studies in cross-border cooperation have emerged in the second half of the 20th century, including on the concept and categories of cross-border cooperation.

The Madrid Convention defines cross-border cooperation as “any concerted action designed to reinforce and foster neighbourly relations between territorial communities or authorities within the jurisdiction of two or more Contracting Parties and the conclusion of any agreement and arrangement necessary for this purpose. Transfrontier co-operation shall take place in the framework of territorial communities’ or authorities’ powers”⁴. Cross-border cooperation means any form of cooperation across borders between neighbourlands and neighbourlanders. Cross-border cooperation shapes partnerships between local and regional stakeholders that are separated by state border, having repercussions on both sides of the border. The aim of cross-border cooperation is “to foster the harmonious development of border communities”⁵. Any arrangement for cross-border cooperation originates with the “recognition of a given problem; and policy choices”⁶. The success of cross-border cooperation is “based on concrete issues and has concrete goals”⁷.

² European Commission, “Cross-Border Cooperation,” accessed July 21, 2019, https://ec.europa.eu/neighbourhood-enlargement/neighbourhood/cross-border-cooperation_en.

³ European Commission, “Eastern Partnership,” accessed 21 July 2019, https://ec.europa.eu/neighbourhood-enlargement/neighbourhood/eastern-partnership_en.

⁴ Council of Europe, European Outline Convention on Transfrontier Co-operation between Territorial Communities or Authorities, Madrid, 21.05.1980, accessed 21 July 2019, <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/rms/0900001680078b0c>.

⁵ Daniele Del Bianco and John Jackson, *Cross-Border Cooperation Toolkit* (Council of Europe: Strasbourg, 2012), 11.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 15.

⁷ *Ibid.*, 20.

The joint handbook *Practical Guide to Cross-Border Cooperation*, elaborated with the support of the Association of European Border Regions, falls into three parts on cross-border cooperation: the framework – motives for cross-border cooperation, experience to date, legal instruments facilitating cross-border cooperation, EU level initiatives and programmes, technical requirements; cooperation structures – stages of cooperation and appropriate structures, cooperation structures at strategic (programme) level, cooperation structures at project level; and examples of good practice – spatial planning, economic development, transport and infrastructure, tourism, environment, training, education and labour market development, health and social services, culture and media, agriculture and development. The authors highlight that “the main motives for cross-border cooperation are:

- the transformation of the border from a line of separation into a place for communication between neighbours;
- the overcoming of mutual animosities and prejudices between peoples of border regions which result from historical heritage;
- the strengthening of democracy and the development of operational regional/local administrative structures;
- the overcoming of national peripherality and isolation;
- the promotion of economic growth and development and the improvement of the standards of living;
- the rapid assimilation into or approach towards an integrated Europe”⁸.

There are provided successful principles, originated in the basic requirements of European aid programmes, for “cross-border cooperation:

- partnership;
- subsidiarity;
- the existence of a common cross-border development concept or programme;
- joint structures on regional/local level and independent sources of financing”⁹.

In the process of cross-border cooperation on the external EU borders to “Central and Eastern Europe, the focus is more on:

- building up young democracies and administrative structures;
- upgrading infrastructure and opening new border crossings;
- improving transport and the communication networks;
- economic development;
- eliminating economic disparities on both sides of the border;
- improving environmental protection in all areas;
- greater participation in future INTERREG programmes and their management;

and

- doing a better job of combining EU resources with those of Phare CBC and TACIS CBC”¹⁰.

The role of border in cross-border cooperation is very complex; it may be multiple as well: a border “can be a barrier but it can also be a gateway, an opportunity and a

⁸ Jens Gabbe, Viktor von Malchus, and Haris Martinos, *Practical Guide to Cross-Border Cooperation* (Gronau: Association of European Border Regions, 2000), 7.

⁹ Ibid., 13–14.

¹⁰ Ibid., 23.

resource”¹¹. Cross-border cooperation “brings together the communities on both sides of the border. It helps to transform the border into a possibility for development”¹². Thus, borderlanders can benefit from their borders.

Cross-border cooperation changes border regions¹³. Luis De Sousa identifies among the drivers of cross-border cooperation as economic drivers, political leadership drivers, geographical drivers, cultural/identity and state formation drivers¹⁴. Additionally, the determinants of cross-border cooperation play an essential role as well: leadership, organizational capacity, supportive institutions, a spatial dynamic, rapid change, existing networks and an economic cost¹⁵.

In a very straightforward manner Jen Nelles and Olivier Walther warn about borders in space and borders in mind¹⁶ that could determine opportunities or obstacles in cross-border cooperation.

Scientific approach of cross-border cooperation is also very important for stakeholders. Gathering data and improved knowledge on cross-border cooperation stimulates building viable partnerships in border regions as cross-border collaboration involves a high degree of interoperability and common approaches of border communities that are based on mutual trust and understanding between actors that in most cases operate in very diverse legal, economic and cultural environments.

Legal Framework

Cross-border cooperation legal framework has been developing throughout the years. It represents the legal background for cooperation with the neighbours. For geographical reasons it is fair to divide the regulatory acts into two parts:

- *national* acts;
- *bilateral* acts fall into two groups:
 - agreements concluded between Moldova and the European Union;
 - agreements concluded between Moldova and Romania;
 - agreements concluded between Moldova and Ukraine.

National acts on cross-border cooperation include basically the Concept of Cross-Border Cooperation (2004) and the National Strategy for Regional Development (2016) with subsequent completions and modifications.

Basic bilateral acts concluded between Moldova and the European Union are: the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Moldova, of the other part (1998) and the Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic

¹¹ Pekka Jarvio, *Cross-Border Cooperation – Benefiting from Borders* (Helsinki: Edita Plc, 2011), 2.

¹² *Ibid.*, 4.

¹³ Luis De Sousa, “Understanding European Cross-Border Cooperation: A Framework for Analysis,” *Journal of European Integration*, 35, no. 6 (2012): 2–4, accessed July 12, 2019, DOI: 10.1080/07036337.2012.711827.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, 12–16.

¹⁵ Todd Hataley and Christian Leuprecht, “Determinants of Cross-Border Cooperation,” *Journal of Borderlands Studies*, 33, no. 3 (2018): 317–328, accessed July 10, 2019, DOI: 10.1080/08865655.2018.1482776.

¹⁶ Jen Nelles and Olivier Walther, “Changing European Borders: From Separation to Interface? An Introduction,” *Articulo. Journal of Urban Research*, 6 (2011), accessed July 16, 2019, DOI: 10.4000/articulo.1658.

Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Moldova, of the other part (2014).

The acts concluded between Moldova and Romania are: Protocol between the Border Guard Service of the Republic of Moldova and the General Inspectorate of the Romanian Border Police within the Ministry of Administration and Interior of Romania on information exchange in the view of carrying out specific missions (2005); Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Moldova and the Government of Romania on mutual travelling of the citizens (2006); Agreement between the Republic of Moldova and the European Community on readmission (2007); Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Moldova and the Government of Romania on local border traffic (2009); Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Moldova and the Government of Romania on state border crossing points between the Republic of Moldova and Romania (2009); Treaty between the Republic of Moldova and Romania on state border regime, cooperation and mutual assistance on border-related issues (2010) not in force; Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Moldova and the Government of Romania on establishment and functioning of the Galati Joint Contact Centre (2011); Regulation on organization and functioning of the Galati Joint Contact Centre (2013); Protocol between the Border Guard Service of the Republic of Moldova and the Ministry of Administration and Interior of Romania through the General Inspectorate of Border Police on strengthening cooperation at central and territorial levels (2011).

The acts concluded between Moldova and Ukraine are: Treaty between the Republic of Moldova and Ukraine on state border (1999); Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Moldova and the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine on regime of usage of the Odessa-Reni Ukrainian highway crossing the territory of the Republic of Moldova, and the land sector crossed by it (2001); Agreement between the Republic of Moldova and the Government of Ukraine on readmission of persons at Moldova-Ukraine state border (1997); Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Moldova and the Government of Ukraine on organization of joint control in border crossing points at Moldova-Ukraine state border (1997); Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Moldova and the Government of Ukraine on border crossing points at the Moldova-Ukraine state border and simplified border crossing procedures for citizens residing in border districts” (1997); Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Moldova and the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine on visa-free travel of citizens (2001); Protocol between the Border Guard Troops Department of the Republic of Moldova and the State Committee for state border guard of Ukraine on interaction in Moldova-Ukraine state border crossing points (2001); Protocol between the Border Guard Troops Department of the Republic of Moldova and the State Committee for state border guard of Ukraine on interaction to ensure protection of the Moldova-Ukraine state border (2003); Protocol between the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Moldova, the Border Guard Troops Department of the Republic of Moldova and the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, the State Committee for state border guard of Ukraine on return of persons at Moldova-Ukraine state border (2003); Protocol between the Border Guard Troops Department of the Republic of Moldova, Customs Service of the Republic of Moldova and the Administration of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine, Customs Service of Ukraine on organization of joint control in the international road border crossing point “Criva-Mamalîga” (2004); Protocol between the Border Guard Troops Department, Customs Department of the Republic of Moldova and Administration of the State Border Guard Service, Customs Service of Ukraine on organization of joint control in

“Medveja-Zelenaia” local road BCP (2004); Protocol between the Border Guard Troops Department, Customs Department of the Republic of Moldova and Administration of the State Border Guard Service, Customs Service of Ukraine on organization of joint control in “Larga-Kelmenti” international road BCP (2004); Protocol between the Border Guard Troops Department, Customs Department of the Republic of Moldova and Administration of the State Border Guard Service, Customs Service of Ukraine on organization of joint control in “Briceni-Rossoshany” international road BCP (2004); Protocol between the Border Guard Troops Department, Customs Department of the Republic of Moldova and Administration of the State Border Guard Service, Customs Service of Ukraine on organization of joint control in “Giurgiulești-Reni” international road BCP (2004); Protocol between the Border Guard Troops Department of the Republic of Moldova and Administration of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine on activity of border representatives (2005); Protocol between the Border Guard Service of the Republic of Moldova and Administration of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine on cooperation of operative bodies (2005); Protocol as of 29 May 2006 between the Government of the Republic of Moldova and the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine on amendment and supplement of the Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Moldova and the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine on border crossing points at the Moldova-Ukraine state border and simplified border crossing procedures for citizens residing in border districts (1997); Protocol between the Border Guard Service of the Republic of Moldova and Administration of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine on information exchange (2006); Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Moldova and the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine on joint border patrolling (2011); Protocol between the Border Guard Service of the Republic of Moldova, Customs Service of the Republic of Moldova and Administration of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine, Customs Service of Ukraine on the experiment of carrying out joint control in “Briceni-Rossoshany” BCP on the territory of Ukraine (2011); Protocol between the Border Guard Service of the Republic of Moldova and Administration of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine on organization of joint patrolling at Moldova-Ukraine border (2012).

The synthetic regulatory framework of cross-border cooperation has been developed gradually between Moldova and its neighbours: with one organization – the European Union and two states – Romania and Ukraine. In the following it is revealed how the legal framework of cross-border cooperation works among neighbouring partners.

Institutionalization of Cross-Border Cooperation

Cross-border cooperation is an important component of the regional policy of the European Union, which is widely regarded as an investment policy, supporting job creation, competitiveness, economic growth, improved quality of life and sustainable development. Cross-border cooperation was a key priority of the European Neighbourhood and Partnership Instrument (ENPI), an important funding tool of the European Union, being replaced by the European Neighbourhood Instrument (ENI) and following to create an area of shared values, stability and prosperity, enhanced cooperation, deeper economic and regional integration by covering a wide range of cooperation areas.

Cross-border cooperation varies in its forms of materialization. Cross-border cooperation covers informal forms and formal (institutionalized) forms. At institutional level, the forms of cross-border cooperation are: (1) *Euroregions* and similar bodies (“can have different legal forms or organization, but they share a number of common

characteristics: they are permanent; they have an identity separate from their members; they have their own administrative, technical and financial resources; and their own internal decision making. The geographical area they cover is determined not only by the administrative units, but also by the extent of socio-economic integration. They are not a new level of local or regional government but rather an interchange point for existing public and private sector bodies”¹⁷); (2) *working communities* (“structures, typically without legal form, resulting from signing a protocol of co-operation or a legally non-binding agreement between regional or local authorities that agreed to cooperate. They can be distinguished by a number of common features: they are permanent; they often retain the identity of their members; they do not have substantial financial and personnel resources of their own; and they rarely have their own decision making structures”¹⁸), and (3) *Interreg or other EU programmes* (“created specifically to manage the implementation of such programmes and have at least a programme monitoring committee and secretariat”¹⁹).

For our research on cross-border cooperation between Moldova with the European Union, Romania and Ukraine are pertinent the institutionalised forms of Euroregions and programmes.

Euroregions

The Euroregions are associative networks that bring together regions in achieving sustainable management. The Euroregions support cross-border cooperation inside the European Union and at its external borders with neighbouring countries by reinforcing common development strategies for better life and social security²⁰.

The Euroregions are important drivers of cross-border cooperation. The Association of European Border Regions sets the following “criteria for the identification of Euroregions:

- an association of local and regional authorities on either side of the national border, sometimes with a parliamentary assembly;
- a transfrontier association with a permanent secretariat and a technical and administrative team with own resources;
- of private law nature, based on non-profit-making associations or foundations on either side of the border in accordance with the respective national law in force;
- of public law nature, based on inter-state agreements, dealing among other things, with the participation of territorial authorities”²¹.

Moldova has been involved as a member and participating party in the activities of four Eastern European Euroregions:

- the Upper Prut Euroregion – including Botoşani county and Suceava county from Romania; Bălţi municipality, Briceni district, Edineţ district, Făleşti district, Glodeni district, Ocnîţa district, Râşcani district and Sângerei district from Moldova; Chernivtsi

¹⁷ Friederike Welter et al., *Cross-Border Partnerships in Belarus, Moldova and Ukraine and the Consequences of EU-Enlargement* (Siegen: PRO KMU, 2007), 4–5.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*, 5.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*

²⁰ Vasile Cucerescu, “EU Cross-Border Cooperation in Eastern Europe,” in “Cross-Border Cooperation in Europe between Successes and Limits,” ed. Constantin-Vasile Țoca, Klára Czimre and Vasile Cucerescu, *EuroTimes* (Oradea: Oradea University Press) 21 (Spring 2016): 107–128.

²¹ European Parliament, Committee of Regional Development, Report on the Role of “Euroregions” in the Development of Regional Policy, 22.06.2005.

region and Ivano-Frankivsk region from Ukraine – with the focus on economic projects, infrastructure, environmental projects, cultural and humanitarian activities;

- the Siret-Prut-Nistru Euroregion – including Iași county, Vaslui county and Prahova county from Romania and 26 districts out of 32 from Moldova – with the focus on opportunities for development and common challenges;

- the Lower Danube Euroregion – including Galați county, Brăila county and Tulcea county from Romania; Odessa region and Reni district from Ukraine; Cahul district and Cantemir district from Moldova – with the focus on sustainable development through deepening cooperation between partners;

- the Dniester Euroregion – including Vinnitsa region from Ukraine **and** Ocnîța, Soroca, Florești, Șoldănești, Rezina and Dondușeni districts from Moldova – with the focus on cooperation in economy, science, education, culture, tourism and sports²².

As it is shown these Euroregions are restricted geographically to local authorities in the border regions functioning on the top-down principle. Even if the Euroregions faced legal inconsistencies they contributed at a high or low degree to the border regions.

Cross-Border Cooperation Programmes

Cross-border cooperation programmes represent direct access to EU funding by which Moldovan authorities benefit expressly. Cross-border cooperation programmes are ensured by EU financing tools. Usually EU financing tools correspond to financial exercises of the European Union. During 2007–2013 cross-border cooperation programmes were financed by the European Neighbourhood and Partnership Instrument (ENPI) and during 2014–2020 cross-border cooperation programmes are financed by the European Neighbourhood Instrument (ENI).

Within the European Neighbourhood and Partnership Instrument (ENPI), Moldova participated in three cross-border and transnational programmes as mentioned below.

(1) Joint Operational Programme Romania-Ukraine-Moldova²³ aimed at improving the economic, social and environmental situation in the program area of secure borders through increased contact between partners on each side of the border.

The programme priorities focused on: towards a more competitive border economy; environmental challenges and emergency preparedness; promotion of people to people cooperation.

Eligible areas covered: Botoșani, Galați, Iași, Suceava, Tulcea and Vaslui counties (Romania), plus the adjacent Brăila county; Odessa and Chernivtsi regions (Ukraine), plus the adjacent Ivano-Frankivsk and Vinnitsia regions, 10 districts of Khmelnytskyi region (Vinkovetskyi, Chemerovetskyi, Khmelnytskyi, Kamyanets-Podilskyi, Letychivskyi, Dunayevetskyi, Derazhnyanskyi, Novoushutskyi, Yarmolynetskyi and Horodetskyi) and 12 districts of Ternopil region (Ternopilskyi, Berezhanskyi, Pidgayetskyi, Kozivskyi, Pidvolochyskyi, Terebovlyanskyi, Monasturskyi, Gusyatynskyi, Chortkivskyi, Borshchivskyi, Zalizhutskyi and Buchatskyi); and the whole territory of Moldova.

Moldova participated in the following projects with *national impact*: Improvement of Border-Cooperation between Moldova and Romania on food and petroleum products IMPEFO; Creating a border communications infrastructure – a factor

²² For more details on Euroregions see Cucerescu.

²³ Joint Operational Programme Romania-Ukraine-Moldova, accessed July 22, 2019, <http://www.ro-ua-md.net/en/>.

of sustainable socio-economic development and spatial planning complex; Gas pipeline to interconnect the natural gas transmission system in Romania and natural gas transmission system in the Republic of Moldova in the direction Iași (Romania) – Ungheni (Moldova); Feasibility Study for the synchronous interconnection of electric power systems in Ukraine and Moldova with the continental European electricity transmission system ENTSO-E; Improvement of the responsiveness of the Mobile Emergency Service for Resuscitation and Extrication (SMURD) through a common integrated system for effective monitoring and mitigation of disaster consequences, for the populations within the common borders of Romania, Ukraine and Moldova; Inventory, assessment and remediation of anthropogenic pollution sources in the Lower Danube region of Ukraine, Romania and Moldova; Prevention and protection against flooding in the river basins of the Siret and Prut rivers, through the implementation of a modern monitoring system with automated stations – EAST AVERT; Strengthening the network of natural protected areas for biodiversity protection and sustainable development in the Danube Delta and the Lower Prut region – Nature PAN; Promotion of sustainable production and implementation of best practices in cattle farms of cross-border region; East European Network for Excellence in Research and Development in the Field of Chronic Disease CHRONEX-RD; Cross-Border Support Centre for assisted development of zootechny; Forming a network of infrastructure innovation entities in the cross border region; Business cross-border cooperation RO-UA-MD; Cross-border interdisciplinary cooperation for prevention of natural disaster and mitigation of environmental pollution in the Lower Danube Euroregion; Improving human competitiveness through synergies in the border region; Strengthening of communication relations between the blind in cross-border region; Cultural and artistic education in the context of sustainable cross border cooperation; Sustainability principles into the concept of integrated territorial development of urban cross-border settlements; Lead Your Way to Business; REGIOCULT – cultural identity in Romania and Moldova; Together for children; and in the following projects with *regional impact*: Development of cross-border tourism by promoting the Manuc Bey manor, Elena Ioan Cuza funerary complex and Blesciunov manor; Rehabilitation of the medieval royal court of Lăpușna for sightseeing; Safety and information systems in traffic; Centre for Cross-Border Business Support – Training, Exhibition and Symposium; TransAgRomaniapolis TransfRomaniantier AgRomaniabusiness Support; Cross-Border Inventory of Degraded Land – CRING; Cross-border management tool of waste for rural communities, CBCRurWaste; Emergency situations medicine – prompt response to cross border challenges; Pure water – for the benefit of villagers; Development of water management in the village Tulucești, Galați county and in village Sireți, Strășeni district; As different as we are – seven ethnicities at the Black Sea; Unity in Diversity – Traditional exchanges of Arts and Crafts for Youth; Professional training network for local government; Cross-border and cross-institutional network for the prevention of abuse in the field of children’s rights protection; Preventing and combating human trafficking by developing cross border cooperation, cross-institutional network and increasing awareness of the vulnerable people; Get information on time: Human trafficking EXISTS; Development and management of integrated urban development plans; Cross-border cooperation in combating human trafficking; Prevention of old age crisis in Romania and Republic of Moldova; Professional ethics in dealing with minors; Educational Park – model of cooperation in environmental education; Alternative model of entrepreneurship education; Creation of a trilateral cross border network for development and marketing of the agro-

alimentary local and traditional products in the Lower Danube cross border area; SIDE BY SIDE – Trinodal network for tourism development and promotion in the cross-border region Galați-Cahul-Reni; Internationalization and Networking of SMEs and business support structures in the cross border area; ENERGY – cross-border good; Increasing the capacity of waste management for a cleaner environment in cities Vaslui and Cahul; Business environment – Sustainable development and promotion; IMAGINE – Improved Methods for Assuring the Growth and Innovation in the North Lower Danube Euro Region; Understating autism; Children’s Music Festival “Music for everyone”; Creation of a trilateral cross border network for development and marketing of the agro-alimentary local and traditional products in the Lower Danube cross-border area; Joint cultural promotion – means of developing Euroregional cooperation in the Lower Danube; Cross-border cooperation in social services; Folk costume: unity and variety in the Lower Danube; Development of cooperation in the field of social and medical services for young people in the border region Galați-Cahul EURO – HEALTH; I am not for sale – Say Stop Human Trafficking; Fanfare across borders; Development of the agricultural sector through the creation of a cross-border agricultural network; ECO CARPAȚI – Development of cross-border business in the Carpathians as an opportunity to improve economic competitiveness; Joint Centre for Business Support – a tool encouraging entrepreneurship development in the cross-border region RO-UA-MD; Medieval Jewels: Hotin, Soroca, Suceava Castles; Protecting borders against the threat of stray animals; Improvement of cross-border management of solid waste in Republic of Moldova, Romania and Ukraine; Improvement of cross-border management of solid waste in Republic of Moldova, Romania and Ukraine; Increase of life activity safety in the valley of the river Prut; Improving the ecological situation of basins of Prut and Dniester by improving sewage treatment systems in Chernivtsi and Drochia; Virtual Platform for Cross-Border Youth Exchange; The cross-border network for organic farming, “EcoAgriNet 2”; The green movement among young people in the cross-border region; The road is everybody’s! – Young people learn rules of traffic safety; Performance management and administrative efficiency; It is time for science; Culture without borders; Think Green; CrossLife-SkillsNet; Internet: E-friend; Cross-border exchanges in professional education; The green movement among young people in the cross-border region; Eco-towns – a shared vision in the cross-border region; Reducing pollution and soil erosion by expanding waste management capacity; Beyond borders – Music and identity amongst European youth; I care, I get involved!

(2) Black Sea Basin Joint Operational Programme 2007–2013²⁴ had the aim to develop strong regional partnerships and close cooperation in the Black Sea Basin (development of local government, shared values, gender equality, reducing gender discrimination, valuing women’s contribution to economic and social development, improving the environmental sustainability of activities, cultural integration and interchange).

The priorities of the programme were: to support cross-border partnerships for economic and social development based on combined resources; to share resources and competencies for environmental protection and conservation; to support cultural and educational initiatives for the establishment of a common cultural environment in the Black Sea Basin.

²⁴ Black Sea Basin Joint Operational Programme, accessed 22 July 2019, <https://blacksea-cbc.net/>.

Eligible areas covered: South-East Region (Romania); Severoiztochen, Yugoiztochen (Bulgaria); Kentriki Makedonia, Anatoliki Makedonia Thraki (Greece); Istanbul, Tekirdağ, Kocaeli, Zonguldak, Kastamonu, Samsun, Trabzon (Turkey); Odessa, Mykolaiv, Kherson, Zaporoshye and Donetsk, Crimea and Sevastopol (Ukraine); whole territories of Armenia, Georgia, Moldova.

Moldova participated in the following projects with *national impact*: Industrial Symbiosis Network for Environment Protection and Sustainable Development in Black Sea Basin (SymNet); Facilitate the trade of agro-food products in the Black Sea Basin (FTAP); Capacity for Integrated Urban Development: INTEGRABLE; Preparation conditions for Black Sea coasts wines penetration on the international market; e-fairs and Networking Expositions; Creation of the Black Sea Network for sustainable development of tourism in Bulgaria, Romania, Ukraine and Georgia; Black Sea Network for Sustainable Tourism – Marketing Strategies common tourism and development in the Black Sea Region; Networks of cooperation between multiple levels of actors to promote quality standards for heritage tourism across borders; Development of Outdoor Adventure Tourism Network in Black Sea Region; Network of local/regional economical development as critical leverage point for increasing competitiveness in the regions of the Black Sea Basin; Network of regional development of the Black Sea Basin; Regional network of business incubators; Black Sea Earthquake Safety Network; Scientific network for prevention of earthquakes, landslides and floods risks; Research networking for the environmental monitoring and mitigation of adverse ecological effects in the Black Sea Basin; Regional cooperation for environmental protection of the Black Sea against agricultural polluters; Collective protection of skills from researchers to farmers for sustainable and ecological exploitation of agricultural and environmental protection; Strategy of continuous improvement of the effectiveness of treatment plants in the Black Sea countries; Black Sea network promoting the integrated natural wastewater treatment systems; Using flow in forest fire suppression with the help of new technologies; Less waste in the Northwest region of the Black Sea; Master Degree Program under the Black Sea Universities Network on the management of renewable energy sources; Black Sea – unity and diversity in the Roman antiquity; Maritime Network of Education for the Development of Maritime Culture in the Black Sea Basin; Effective management of lifelong learning in the Black Sea Basin network; Collaboration Network at the Black Sea; Platform for cultural exchange – Culture-EXP; Black Sea people living history; in the following projects with *regional impact*: Tradition and Originality, Uniqueness and Wealth to achieve an Innovative Approach in order to develop tourism in the Black Sea region; Quality certification system in agro-tourism – CerTour; Introducing innovative waste management practices in selected cities in Georgia, Moldova and Armenia, GMA-WMP; A clean environment for our future; Black Sea Buildings Energy Efficiency Plan – BSBEPP; Tourist Trails in the Coastal Region – BSB TOUR; Danube Black Sea connection of the European economy with the Asian economy, an important step in the development of the Black Sea Basin; Clean Rivers – Clean Sea! Joint action of environmental NGOs in the Black Sea Basin; Improving integrated coastal zone management in the Black Sea region; Innovative tools for environmental analysis in north-western Black Sea Basin; Interpretative in land trails: support for the management of natural protected areas in the Black Sea; Raising Public Awareness on Solid Municipal Waste Management in the North –West of the Black Sea Region; Excellence in the Public Sector.

(3) Transnational Cooperation Programme “South-East Europe”²⁵ aimed at improving the territorial, economic and social integration process in South East Europe and contributing to cohesion, stability and competitiveness of the area through the development of transnational partnerships.

Priority axes were: facilitation of innovation and entrepreneurship; protection and improvement of the environment; improvement of the accessibility; development of transnational synergies for sustainable growth areas.

Eligible areas involved community support for regions in 16 countries – Member States, candidate countries, potential candidate countries and third countries: Albania, Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Romania, Croatia, Greece, Hungary, Serbia, Montenegro, Slovakia, Slovenia, Macedonia, Moldova; Lombardia, Bolzano/Bozen, Trento, Veneto, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Emilia Romagna, Umbria, Marche, Abruzzo, Molise, Puglia Basilicata regions (Italy); Chernivtsi, Ivano-Frankivsk, Zakarpattia and Odessa regions (Ukraine).

Moldova participated in the following projects with *national impact*: Intelligent Cluster Policies in South East Europe (ClusterPoliSEE); Cooperation of science parks in South East Europe for promotion of introduction of research and development technologies of SMEs on the transnational market; Establishing support mechanisms for innovation and increasing awareness of the potential for innovation, research and development in the food industry in the South-East European regions (Inno-Food SEE); Convention for waste management for inland navigation on the Danube (CO WANDA); Anchoring the Danube River Network of Protected Areas as Platform for Preservation of Danube Natural Heritage (DANUBEPARKS STEP 2.0); Widening the Thermal Solar Energy Exploitation by the Successful Models (Wide the SEE by Succ Mod); Hydropower targeted to improve water resource management for a growing renewable energy production (SEE HYDROPOWER); Road safety in South East European regions (ROSEE); South East Neighbourhood Safe Routes (SENSOR); Sustainable Transport and Tourism along the Danube (TRANSDANUBE); Integrated Urban Development of Vital Historic Towns as Regional Centres in South East Europe (ViTo); The Spatial Development Concept of Interregional Co-operation in the Danube Space (DONAUREGIONEN+); Sustainable Transport and Tourism along the Danube (TRANSDANUBE); and in the following projects with *regional impact*: Transnational integrated management of water resources in agriculture for the European WATER emergency control (EU. Water); Establishment and promotion of new approaches and tools for the strengthening of primary sector’s competitiveness and innovation in the South East Europe (APP4INNO); Launching local level heritage entrepreneurship: strategies and tools to unite forces, safeguard the place, mobilize cultural values, and deliver the experience (SAGITTARIUS); Strategic Territorial Agendas for “Small and Middle-Sized Towns” Urban Systems (STATUS).

Within the European Neighbourhood Instrument (ENI) Moldova has been participating in four cross-border and transnational programmes as mentioned below.

(1) Joint Operational Programme Romania-Moldova²⁶ aims at contributing to a region of prosperity and good neighbourliness through soft and hard investment projects.

The programme priorities are: institutional cooperation in the educational field for increasing access to education and quality of education; promotion and support for

²⁵ Transnational Cooperation Programme “South-East Europe,” accessed 22 July 2019, <http://www.southeast-europe.net/>.

²⁶ Joint Operational Programme Romania-Moldova.

research and innovation; preservation and promotion of the cultural and historical heritage; development of cross border transport and ICT infrastructure; support to the development of health services and access to health; support to joint activities for the prevention of natural and man-made disasters as well as joint actions during emergency situations; prevention and fight against organized crime and police cooperation.

The programme area covers: Botoşani, Iaşi, Vaslui, and Galaţi counties, including adjacent the cities of Bucharest, Neamţ, Bacău and and Suceava; the whole territory of Moldova.

For the time being, there have been contracted a few projects by the technical secretariat.

(2) Black Sea Basin Joint Operational Programme 2014–2020²⁷ aims at improving the welfare of the people in the Black Sea basin regions through sustainable growth and joint environmental protection (business, entrepreneurship, environmental protection, reduction of marine litter).

The priorities of the programme are: to promote jointly business and entrepreneurship in the tourism and cultural sectors; to increase cross-border trade opportunities and modernization in the agricultural and connected sectors; to improve joint environmental monitoring; to promote common awareness-raising and joint actions to reduce river and marine litter.

Area of implementation includes: the whole territories of Moldova, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia; Bulgaria (NUTS II regions Severoiztochen and Yugoiztochen), Greece (NUTS II regions Anatoliki Makedonia, Kentriki Makedonia and Thraki), Romania (NUTS II Southeast Region), Turkey (NUTS equivalent II region of İstanbul, Tekirdağ, Kocaeli, Zonguldak, Kastamonu, Samsun and Trabzon), Ukraine (regions of Odessa, Mykolaiv, Kherson, Donetsk Zaporoshye, Autonomous Republic of Crimea and city of Sevastopol).

For the time being, the list of awarded projects with Moldova's participation is as follows: Sustainable Agricultural Trade Network in Black Sea Basin; Black Sea Joint Environmental Monitoring and Protection; Marine and River Litter Elimination New Approach; Waste Free Rivers for a Clean Black Sea; Joint Cultural Heritage – Source for Development of Entrepreneurship in the Black Sea Basin; Black Sea Basin interdisciplinary cooperation network for sustainable joint monitoring of environmental toxicants migration, improved evaluation of ecological state and human health impact of harmful substances, and public exposure prevention; Creating a System of Innovative Transboundary Monitoring of the Transformations of the Black Sea River Ecosystems under the Impact of Hydropower Development and Climate Change; Green tourism and historical heritage – a stepping stone for the development of the Black Sea Basin; Increase Trading and Modernization of the Beekeeping and Connected Sectors in the Black Sea Basin; Trade and Innovation in Wine Industry; Sustainable Use of Natural Resources – Integrated Services Establishment²⁸. As it turns out Moldova is involved in about half of selected projects under this financing tool.

²⁷ Black Sea Basin Joint Operational Programme.

²⁸ Black Sea Basin Joint Operational Programme, “List of Awarded Projects,” accessed July 22, 2019, <https://blacksea-cbc.net/projects/our-projects/>.

(3) Danube Transnational Cooperation Programme ²⁹ aims at supporting development with transnational in research, technology development, innovation, environmental protection, resource efficiency, sustainable transport and infrastructure promotion, institutional capacity building and efficient public administration.

The programme priorities are: to improve framework conditions for innovation; to increase competences for business and social innovation; to strengthen transnational water management and flood risk prevention; to foster sustainable use of natural and cultural heritage and resources; to foster the restoration and management of ecological corridors; to improve preparedness for environmental risk management; to support environmentally-friendly and safe transport systems and balanced accessibility of urban and rural areas; to improve energy security and energy efficiency; to improve institutional capacities to tackle major societal challenges; to support governance and implementation of the EUSDR.

The programme area includes 9 EU countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Germany (Baden-Württemberg and Bavaria), Hungary, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia; and 5 non-EU countries: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Moldova, Montenegro, Serbia, Ukraine (Ivano-Frankivsk, Chernivtsi, Zakarpattia and Odessa regions).

Selected projects with Moldova's participation are: Improving Administrative Procedures and Processes for Danube IWT; Transnational Cluster Cooperation active on Agro – food, based on Smart Specialization Approach in Danube region; Embracing failure to facilitate second-chance entrepreneurship in the Danube region; Bridging the Danube Protected Areas towards a Danube Habitat Corridor; Danube Ports Network; Danube River Basin Enhanced Flood Forecasting Cooperation; Regional and Transport Development in the Danube-Black Sea Region towards a Transnational Multiport Gateway Region; Leveraging Finance 4 positive Social Change; High-performance Computing for Effective Innovation in the Danube Region; Strengthening social innovation and entrepreneurial spirit of secondary schools' students by using highly innovative Learning System; Fostering Innovation in the Danube Region through Knowledge Engineering and IPR Management; Targeted capacity building of VET partnerships in the Danube Region for the effective modernisation of VET systems; Linking transnational, multimodal traveller information and journey planners for environmentally-friendly mobility in the Danube Region; Transnational Cooperation to transform knowledge into marketable products and services for the Danubian sustainable society of tomorrow; Mobilising Institutional Learning for Better Exploitation of Research and Innovation for the Circular Economy; Risk Assessment on Danube Area Roads; Changing Discourses, Changing Practices: The Roma as Human Resource; Facilitating macro-regional scope and link up to socio-economic actors of Research Infrastructure in the Danube Region; Strengthening Social Entrepreneurial Landscape through involving socially responsible corporate Practices in Entrepreneurial Competences and Skills enhancement in the DANUBE region; Sediment-quality Information, Monitoring and Assessment System to support transnational cooperation for joint Danube Basin water management; Transdanube.Pearls – Network for Sustainable Mobility along the Danube; Fostering the Young Women Entrepreneurship in the Danube Region ³⁰.

²⁹ Danube Transnational Cooperation Programme, accessed 22 July 2019, <http://www.interreg-danube.eu/>.

³⁰ Danube Transnational Cooperation Programme, "Approved Projects," accessed 22 July 2019, http://www.interreg-danube.eu/approved-projects?approved_project_filter%5Bcall%5D=&approved_project_filter%5Bstatus%5D=&approved_project_filter%5Bpriority%5D=&approved_

(4) Eastern Partnership Territorial Cooperation Programme Moldova-Ukraine³¹ aims at strengthening cross-border contacts between local authorities, communities and civil society organizations to help develop joint solutions to common social and economic development challenges.

The programme priorities are: promotion of closer business links across the border; diversification of income sources and development of alternative employment opportunities in rural areas; solving cross-border environmental problems, enhancing emergency preparedness; promotion of multi-cultural diversity and social integrity of ethnical minorities across the border; facilitation of people-to-people links in social sphere, culture, education and sports with focus on youth issues.

The programme area includes: the whole territory of Moldova, Vinnytsia, Chernivtsi and Odessa regions (Ukraine).

EaPTCM-U awarded the following projects: Common Space for Creative and Cultural Industries; Cross-Border Network for Innovative Agriculture; Developing a territorial early warning system for flood emergencies in the Prut river region; Development of the Ukrainian-Moldavian cross-border production-scientific-educational cluster for processing of winemaking by-products; Enhanced capacity for an efficient waste management in “Lower Danube” Euroregion area; Facilitation of people-to-people links in social, cultural and educational sphere with focus on young care leavers from Republic of Moldova and Chernivtsi region; Healthy way by upgraded cross-border sport infrastructure; Increase of the emergency situations preparedness level of medical structures and population of the regions of Ukraine and Republic of Moldova; Joint Opportunities in Business for Youth; Promotion of Food Heritage in the Lower Danube Region; Rural tourism – a sure step towards boosting the cross-border cooperation between districts of Soroca (Republic of Moldova) and Yampil (Ukraine, Vinnytsia Oblast); Step by Step Towards Separate Collection of the Solid Waste; Strengthening Regional Capacities for Applying Environmentally Friendly Technologies in Integrated Pest Management Systems; Through Sustainable Transport to Clean Environment; Youth in Action.

Within the priority of *stronger connectivity*, sector of *cross-border cooperation*, the European Union has implemented many macro-scale projects in Moldova: Construction of the Jointly Operated Border Crossing Point Palanca on the territory of the Republic of Moldova; Increased Opportunities and Better Living Conditions across the Nistru River; The European Union Border Assistance Mission to Moldova and Ukraine (EUBAM); Support to the Modernisation of Customs Service of Moldova in line with AA Requirements MD 13 ENPI FI 07 17 (MD/19); OPEN Neighbourhood – Media Hub: Networking, on-the-job training and support to media professionals across the EU Neighbourhood area; OPEN Neighbourhood – Communicating for a stronger partnership: connecting with citizens across the Eastern Neighbourhood; Eastern Partnership – Integrated Border Management – Capacity Building Project; Implementation of the Programmatic Cooperation framework with the Council of Europe in the Eastern Partnership; Eastern Partnership Territorial Cooperation Programmes; Support to

project_filter%5Bacronym%5D=&approved_project_filter%5BprojectCountry%5D%5B%5D=MD&approved_project_filter%5B_token%5D=IREC-H9muC0Rh1orJEeJgyIvttvGc_rripErWXCdq8.

³¹ Eastern Partnership Territorial Cooperation Programme Moldova-Ukraine, accessed 22 July 2019, <http://www.eaptc.eu/en/program/view-moldova-ukraine.html>.

implementation of Visa Liberalisation Action Plan; Fixed and Mobile Communications Network for the Border Guard Service in the Republic of Moldova: Phase 2 Horești to Otaci – Infrastructure & IT Equipment; Support to the Programmation of the Single Support Framework in Moldova (2014–2020); Support to the implementation of the agreements between the Republic of Moldova and the EU; Supervision of the Fixed and Mobile Communication Network for the Moldovan Border Guard Service – Ungheni to Giurgiulești; External Results Oriented Monitoring (ROM) of projects and programmes financed by the European Union in the European Neighbourhood region; National Integrity System Assessments in European Neighbourhood East region; Developing Cross Border tourism by promoting the Mansion of Manuc Bey, Elena Ioan Cuza Mortuary Complex and the Blesciunov Mansion; Assistance at the tender supply procedure and the delivery of equipment for Biometric Passports production to the Republic of Moldova; Joint Border patrolling on the Green and Blue Border between Republic of Moldova and Ukraine – Supply of Thermo Vision Vehicles for Moldovan Border Police; Support to UNHCR activities in Eastern Europe in the context of EU Regional Protection Programmes – Phase II; Strengthening Capacities and Cooperation in the Identification of Forged and Falsified Travel Documents at the Moldova-Romania Border; Regional electronic communications regulatory framework harmonization between the EU and the Eastern Partnership Partner Countries; Production and publication of the 2013 Neighbourhood Investment Facility (NIF) and 2014 Neighbourhood Investment Facility (NIF) Annual Operational Reports; Strengthening the Link Between Migration and Development: Testing an Integrated Service Provider to Moldovan Migrants and their Communities; The effects of migration in Moldova and Georgia on children and elderly left behind; Equipment for the introduction of biometric passports in the Republic of Moldova, Lot 1; Local Integration of Refugees in Belarus, Moldova and Ukraine; Consolidation of migration management capacities in the Republic of Moldova; Equipment for the introduction of biometric passports in the Republic of Moldova, Lot 2; Support to the Eastern Partnership Panel on Migration and Asylum; Building Migration Partnerships (BMP) project – A platform for applying the Global Approach to Migration to the Eastern and South-Eastern Regions Neighbouring the European Union; EaP Connect; Enlarged Sustainable Partnership for Decentralization Reform (ESPDR); Technical assistance to the Bureau for Reintegration of the Republic of Moldova; Supporting the implementation of the EC visa facilitation and readmission agreements; Information seminars/press trips for journalists from the EU Member States to the countries of Neighbourhood East; BOMUK 4 – Border Management Improvement: Equipment Supply to the Border Guard Services of Ukraine and Moldova (Lot 1); European Union Border Assistance Mission to Moldova and Ukraine (EUBAM) Phase 10; Remittances Developing Moldovan Communities – Sustainable Use of Remittances by Generating Local Income in the Republic of Moldova; Eastern European Partnership – IBM Flagship Initiative Training Project (EaP IBM FIT); Supporting the Republic of Moldova to implement the EU-Moldova Action Plan on Visa Liberalisation; Support to the Eastern Partnership Panel on Migration and Asylum; The Eastern Partnership Youth Regional Unit; Support to Implementation of EC Readmission Agreements with the Republic of Moldova, the Russian Federation and Ukraine: Facilitation of Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (SIREADA); E-Platform for Neighbourhood; Cross-border cultural activities – premise for a multilateral sustainable cooperation; An integrated approach for the sustainability of the tourism production; Strengthening Migration Management and Cooperation on Readmission in Eastern Europe (MIGRECO);

Preparation of Draft Law on the Transnistrian Settlement Process; Addressing the Negative Effects of Migration on Minors and Families Left Behind; Development of the touristic roads in Nisporeni-Prut cross-border area; Building bridges: linking Europe's neighbourhoods to ensure public finance for public benefit; Supervision of the supply contracts of a fixed and mobile communications network for Border Guard in the Republic of Moldova Phase II Horești to Otaci; Effective government of labour migration and its skills dimensions; Costs assessment: Upgrade and Extension of the Fixed and Mobile Communication Network for the Moldovan Border Guard Service; Eastern Partnership and Black Sea events; Fixed and Mobile Communication Network for the Border Guard Service, Ungheni to Giurgiulești; Supporting the implementation of the migration and development component of the EU-Moldova Mobility Partnership and harnessing its benefits for the residents of the Transnistria Region of the Republic of Moldova; Fixed and Mobile Communications Network for the Border Guard Service in the Republic of Moldova: Phase 2 Horești to Otaci – Radio Equipment, in 1 lot; Facility for the cross border cooperation programmes at the EU's external borders (ENPI CBC) – INTERACT ENPI II; Supporting the implementation of the migration and development component of the EU-Moldova Mobility Partnership; Pre-feasibility Study for Projects to be possibly Funded under the Eastern Partnership Integrated Border Management Flagship Initiative; Assisting the tender procedures for future supervision service contract Phase 2 Fixed and Mobile Communications Network for Border Guards Service; Monitoring of the implementation of the Cross Border Cooperation programmes under the 2007–2013 European Neighbourhood and Partnership Instrument (ENPI); Eastern Partnership cooperation in the fight against irregular migration – Supporting the implementation of the Prague Process Action Plan (EaP-SIPPAP); Preparation of Twinning fiche and ancillary supply contract (including NCTS component) for strengthening the Single Window approach to the Customs Service of the Republic of Moldova³². The allocated funds vary from a couple of thousands of Euro to millions of Euro.

Impact

The long records are compiled for the first time in a paper. They have been presented to show the magnitude of EU engagement and high visibility in cross-border cooperation initiatives implemented in Moldova. The long records highlight quantitative and qualitative support for Moldovan authorities, institutions, organizations and civil society actors. Cross-border cooperation includes soft and hard projects, mono-beneficiaries and multi-beneficiaries, in partnership with other countries and solely for Moldova.

Cross-border cooperation projects contributed to mutual understanding, broader cooperation between decision-makers and other stakeholders, exchange of experiences and good practices, building institutional capacities, solving common problems by identifying common solutions.

There are a lot of learned lessons by participating parties, added value which is of higher importance for sustainable development. Changes for development would have not occurred without substantial support of cross-border cooperation programmes and projects implemented in Moldova for a long time.

³² Delegation of the European Union to Moldova, Projects Funded by the European Union in Moldova, accessed July 23, 2019, <https://www.eu4moldova.md/en>.

Long records demonstrate that large amounts of finances have been oriented towards local beneficiaries; however, effects of implemented projects seem to have low visibility, only for implementation duration, exploited inappropriately in a long run, by beneficiaries. This could be explained to a certain extent by faced multiple challenges: legal differences in financial management, procurement, and incurred costs; inflexible institutional frameworks; insufficiency of qualified human resources; insufficient financial resources or unwillingness of institutional management in supporting applicants to participate in EU programmes; improper institutional and professional capacity as culture as well of participating partners.

All in all, the trend has a positive value for beneficiaries, partners and financing authorities. Cross-border cooperation projects produced and continue to produce the foreseen impact, even if the initiatives address differently to the speed and quality of effects that could be a temporal matter of fact for involved parties. Project results in cross-border cooperation produce irreversible changes in improving border collaboration.

Conclusion

Cross-border cooperation programmes and projects contribute to bringing added value to transfrontier collaboration, to political level, to socio-economic life of the country, to cultural level, to institutional plane, and to people-to-people contacts. In other words, cross-border cooperation programmes and projects build on added value of sustainable development.

The experience of cross-border cooperation programmes and projects reveals a huge move from separation to interface, better governance of borders by understanding and exploiting the benefits from borders. Cross-border cooperation programmes and projects play a crucial role in recreating proximity from negative to positive valences, on the one hand. On the other hand, cross-border cooperation depends on external funds; the quality of cross-border dialogue is yet in progress. Cross-border cooperation needs rather bottom-up than top-down approaches and initiatives to explore all the benefits of borders. Multi-actorness in cross-border cooperation is also needed to create a border for all, a friendly border that unites people of a small country and makes them more cooperative in the region.

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